

Residence Campus Control System

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Abstract: The Residence Campus Control System is designed to enhance safety, efficiency, and sustainability within residential environments by integrating key automated functions. The security gate system restricts unauthorized access by verifying registered users before allowing entry into the campus, thereby ensuring residents' security. The car parking system provides user-friendly parking management, where the entry gate opens only if a parking space is available, and vacant slots are displayed on a screen: eliminating the need for drivers to waste time searching for spaces. Cleanliness is maintained through the dustbin management system, which automatically opens its lid when detecting a person, ensuring hygienic and hands-free waste disposal. When bins are full, the system automatically makes a call and sends an SMS to municipal services, ensuring timely collection. The system also emphasizes the use of renewable energy. It incorporates solar-powered automatic street lights and a solar-powered traffic control system, both of which operate seamlessly during main power failures to ensure uninterrupted public safety. To further maximize efficiency, a sun-tracking system adjusts solar panels to follow the sun's path, significantly boosting energy generation. For disaster preparedness, the fire and earthquake alert systems provide critical early warnings: the earthquake alarm prompts immediate evacuation, while the fire alarm triggers both an audible warning and an automatic emergency notification to the fire service department. Together, these components create a reliable, automated framework for managing residential campuses with enhanced security, sustainability, and resilience.

Keywords: Arduino Project, Dustbin Management System, Earthquake Alert System, Residence Campus Control System, Fire Alert System, Solar-Powered Automatic Street Lights System, Solar-Powered Traffic Control System, Sun-Tracking System.

INTRODUCTION

In today's era of rapid development and modernization, ensuring safety and security within residential campuses has become a top priority. With increasing concerns about unauthorized access and safety risks, there is a strong need for an intelligent and automated system that enhances both security and convenience for residents. The Residence Campus Control System is designed to address these challenges by integrating advanced sensors and smart technologies. The system introduces an automated security gate for controlled entry, real-time parking management, and efficient waste disposal along with disaster detection and solar-powered operation for lighting and traffic regulation within the campus. By combining security, sustainability, and automation, this system provides a scalable solution that transforms residential campuses into safer, smarter, and more efficient living environments.

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PROBLEM

In many residential campuses, the process of controlling entry is still handled manually, which often causes delays, inconvenience, and security risks. Unauthorized access remains a major concern in such areas. Similarly, improper waste collection, lack of organized parking, and power outages affect the comfort and safety of residents. When electricity fails, lighting and essential systems stop functioning, putting residents at risk. Furthermore, the absence of an immediate response plan during emergencies such as fires or earthquakes exposes weaknesses in safety infrastructure. By integrating advanced sensors and automated technologies, the proposed system enhances security through controlled access at the entrance gate, improves waste management, ensures efficient resource usage with renewable energy, and provides real-time alerts for emergency situations.

APPROACH

The project uses a Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) reader and cards to detect people and vehicles at the gate. Authorized vehicles are allowed to pass, and the servo motor opens the toll gate. If the card is unauthorized, the gate remains closed, and access is denied. To deliver the user-friendly parking system, IR sensors are integrated with servo motor and LCD screen. By showing available parking spaces on LCD, drivers can preview the inside parking spaces and it is helpful to save time at finding parking space. If there is available space and when IR sensor at entry detects a vehicle, the servo motor will open the gate door. Otherwise, "Parking is full" is shown on LCD and the gate will not open. In the dustbin management system, to ensure user hygienic and hands-free waste disposal, Ultrasonic sensors located at in front of each dustbin detect people or object. When the sensors detect something, the dustbins' lids will automatically open and close after a few seconds. To ensure timely garbage collection, the Ultrasonic sensors inside the bins check the garbage amount and when they are full, GSM module will automatically call and send SMS notification to the Municipality. Solar-powered systems have been installed to ensure that street lighting and traffic signal systems can continue to operate even during power outages. LDR sensor senses the light density and if the light is less than the predefined threshold, street lights will automatically turn on and street lights will turn off when the light is greater than predefined threshold. For traffic control system, by using Real Time Clock Module (RTC), traffic will work slightly longer in the most traffic congestion time than normal situation. To guarantee the enough power resource, the suntracking system is also deployed in this system by using two LDR sensors to detect light and servo motor to rotate solar panel to follow the sun light. TP4056 Charging Module also serves as intermediate between solar panel and batteries to avoid charging overflow. The system is also integrated with fire and earthquake alert system by using flame sensor, GY61 ADXL335 accelerometer, SIM900A GSM module and buzzer. When the flame sensor detects normal flame, buzzer will only trigger alarm and when it reaches to fire, the system will trigger alarm and continue process of calling and sending SMS notification to fire service department to take action immediately. When the earthquake sensor detects earthquake, buzzer for earthquake system will trigger alarm to notify nearby people.

Figure 1: Block Diagram of Earthquake Alert and Security Gate Management Functions

Figure 2: Block Diagram of Parking and Dustbin Management Functions

Figure 1 illustrates the block diagram for earthquake alert and security gate management functions. In the system, RFID Reader, IR sensor and GY-61 ADXL335 are input devices and Servo Motor, Buzzer, and LCD are output devices. Figure 2 illustrates the block diagram for parking and dustbin management functions. Ultrasonic sensor and IR sensor are input devices. Servo Motors and LCD are output devices.

Figure 3: Block Diagram of Fire Alert and Dustbin Notification Functions

Figure 4: Block Diagram of Solar-Powered Street Light and Traffic Control Functions

Figure 3 illustrates the block diagram for Fire Alert and Dustbin Notification Functions. In the system, Ultrasonic sensor and Flame sensor are input devices and servo motor, buzzer, and GSM module are output devices. Figure 4 illustrates the block diagram for solar-powered street light and traffic control function. RTC module and LDR sensor module are input devices. Street light and Traffic Light are output devices.

Figure 5: Circuit diagram of Earthquake Alert and Entry Gate Management Functions

Figure 5 is the circuit diagram connection between Arduino UNO and other components such as RFID Reader, Servo Motor and LCD, GY-61 ADXL335 and Buzzer.

Figure 6: Circuit diagram of Parking and Dustbin Management Functions

Figure 6 is the circuit diagram connection between Arduino UNO and other components such as IR sensor, Ultrasonic sensor, LCD, and Servo Motor.

Figure 7: Circuit diagram of Fire Alert and Dustbin Notification Functions

Figure 7 is the circuit diagram connection between Arduino UNO and other components such as Ultrasonic sensor, and GSM Module, Flame sensor and Buzzer.

Figure 8: Circuit Diagram of Solar-Powered LED Street Light and Traffic Control Functions

Figure 8 is the circuit diagram connection between Arduino MEGA and other components such as RTC module, Traffic module, Clock Display module, LDR sensor module, Solar Panel, MT3608 voltage converter, Battery charging module, 3.7V Li-ion battery, One channel relay and LED.

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Figure 9: Flow Chart of Security Gate and Car Parking Functions

Figure 10: Flow Chart of Dustbin Management Functions

The Flow chart of the Security Gate and Car Parking System is shown in Figure 9.

- Read the card and if the card is invalid, display “Access Denied” on LCD screen. Otherwise, display “Access Allowed” on LCD screen and the gate will open.
- If there is no available parking space, display “Parking is Full” on LCD and the gate will not open. If not, available parking spaces will show on LCD and the gate will open.

The Flow chart of Dustbin Management System is shown in Figure 10.

- Sense the object and if the is object detected, the dustbin’s lid will open.
- Check the garbage level and if the bin is full, GSM will make phone call and SMS notification.

The Flow chart of Solar-Powered Street Light and Traffic Control System is shown in Figure 11.

- If the left LDR value is greater than the right LDR value, the servo motor rotates the solar panel to the left. Otherwise, rotates the solar panel to the right.
- The generated solar power is stored in the battery and distributed to the system.
- If the light value is below the threshold, the relay switches the street light on. If not, the relay switches street light off.
- If the light value is above the threshold, the relay keeps the street light off.
- If the time is during peak hours (7AM–9AM or 4PM–6PM), the green light duration is set to 25 seconds.
- Otherwise, the green light duration is set to 15 seconds.
- Phase 1: North and South directions show green lights, while East and West directions show red lights.
- When 5 seconds remain, the yellow lights for North and South directions turn on.
- Phase 2: East and West directions show green lights, while North and South directions show red lights.
- When 5 seconds remain, the yellow lights for East and West directions turn on.

The Flow chart of Fire and Earthquake Alert System is shown in Figure 12.

- If the flame sensor detects fire, the buzzer will trigger alarm and continue the process of calling and sending SMS notification to emergency phone number.
- If the earthquake sensor detects earthquake, the buzzer will trigger alarm.

Figure 11: Flow Chart of Solar-Powered Street Light and Traffic

Figure 12: Flow Chart of Fire and Earthquake Alert System

RESULTS

The implementation of the system is shown in Figure 13. For the secure gate system, the working process is shown on LCD screen and the gate will be open by the servo motor. For the car parking system, available parking spaces are shown in LCD screen and the gate door opening process will be processed by the servo motor. Opening the dustbin's lid when the sensor detects object and notifying to municipal staff automatically when the bins are full, are integrated in dustbin management system. Street lights and traffic control system are powered by solar system integrated with suntracking system. In the event of a fire, the system activates a loud alarm while automatically placing a call and sending a SMS with details to the Fire Service Department and in the event of an earthquake, the system activates a loud alarm to notify people.

Figure 13: Implementation Design of the System

CONCLUSION

The Residence Campus Control System enhances safety, convenience, and sustainability within residential areas. RFID technology secures the entry gate by preventing unauthorized access, while the smart parking system ensures efficient use of parking spaces. Cleanliness is maintained through an automated dustbin system with hands-free disposal and timely alerts. Solar-powered streetlights with a tracking mechanism provide reliable lighting and energy efficiency. Fire and earthquake alert modules further strengthen safety by delivering early warnings and emergency notifications. Altogether, the system offers a secure, organized, and eco-friendly solution for modern campus living.

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